

Ecological Literacy of Consumers towards Green Products : A Case Study

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Abstract

Purpose of the Study:Today, consumers choose right products for their family members that are of great value and eco-friendly. The majority of consumers prefer green products and are willing to pay extra for them. It is an attempt to study ecological literacy of consumers towards green products.

Methodology:The data has been collected through primary sources mainly structured questionnaire. Convenience sampling technique has been used to select respondents. Total 125 respondents were selected. Five-point Likert scale, tables and pie charts on percentage basis have been used for analysis and interpretation of the study respectively.

Main Findings:it has been found that major of consumers are aware of green products and its benefits but do not demand due to the fact that they are highly priced and are not well promoted.

Novelty of the Study:This study provides insights into ecological literacy awareness level of consumers towards green products.

Keywords

Ecological Literacy, Green Products, Sustainability, Consumer Behaviour.

Introduction

Increasing awareness of environmental issues has driven a shift in consumer behaviour, leading to a demand for more sustainable products. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the ecological literacy of consumers towards green products or eco-friendly products. The cornerstone of holistic thinking about sustainability is ecological literacy. It fosters the perspective, morality, and manner of conducting activities that promote the way one acts which gives ecological imperatives priority. The goal of ecological literacy is to replace fragmented thinking with new both the social and cognitive abilities required for promoting of sustainable lifestyles.

Ecologically literate consumers are concerned about their buying decisions of products and services that are eco-friendly, sustainable, and have a minimal environmental footprint. As a result, there is a rise in demand for products that are environmentally safe, socially responsible, and ethically sound. Ecologically literate consumers form a sustainable society that prevents the degradation of the environment on which they depend. A substantial rise in focus on green products leads business enterprises and producers to rethink their production and to develop deeper understanding of consumer attitudes and behaviours. They must understand market trends and implement effective marketing strategies.

Objective of study

1. To study the eco-literacy awareness level of consumers with reference to green products.
2. To study the impact of Eco-literacy on consumer purchase behavior towards green products.

Review of Literature

1. **Geetha et al. (2014)**₁ have summarized that even if consumers are willing to pay extra prices for green products, they are not prepared to compensate for the quality of the products to protect the environment. Health benefits, variety and quantity, surroundings and ambience, friends' recommendations, and customer services are some factors that affect customers' buying.
2. **Pillai et al. (2016)** have concluded in the paper that although consumers are aware of the availability of the green products, they are unable to differentiate them from conventional ones due to lack of effective marketing. Additionally, It has been found that respondents perception towards green products are unaffected positively by demographic parameters such as, age, gender, education with the exception of annual family income.
3. **Saluja (2016)** has concluded that variables such as age, gender, occupation, and education have no positive impact on consumer attitudes towards eco-friendly products. Consumers are not influenced by others when making decisions about green products.
4. **Suganya et al (2017)** examined high prices and little consumer awareness of green products prevent consumers from adopting fully green products in their daily

lives. The government and business enterprises have to make efforts to implement green marketing.

5. **Pillai et al (2020)** attempted to know consumers' intentions to buy green products will increase when the quality, awareness, and price of green products are good enough. Industries should also implement strategies to better understand the needs of environmentally conscious consumers and simultaneously preserve the environment for future generations.
6. **Tazeen et al (2022)** attempted to know consumers' awareness, brand value, and product price are influencing factors while making purchasing decisions. Additionally, companies should adopt marketing campaigns to raise more customer awareness.
7. **Vani (2022)** concluded that due to factors like lack of awareness, highly priced, lack of availability of the entire range, poor promotion, difficulty finding products in different stores, and lack of informative labelling of eco-friendly products, there is a decreased demand for eco-friendly products.
8. **Singh (2023)** summarized there is a behaviour-purchase gap among consumers of green cosmetic products. To bridge this gap, the government and big enterprises have to team up.

Methodology

1. **Research design:** Descriptive and analytical research designs have been applied in the study.
2. **Sampling:** Convenient non-probability sampling technique has been adopted for the study.
3. **Sources of data:** The data has been collected through primary sources mainly structured questionnaire, with simple and easy questions. Multiple choice questions and Likert scale questions have been used to answer in the questionnaire. It has been send through e-mail and 125 respondents have filled it.
4. **Research tools:** Questionnaire has been filled with using closed ended questions and five-point Likert scale. Analysis and interpretation of collected data have been assessed with the help of tables and pie charts on percentage basis.

Analysis

1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents.

1.1 Gender Composition

Table 1.1: Gender of Respondents

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	49	39.2%
Female	76	60.8%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 1.1: Gender of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart shows that out of 125 respondents, 39% are male and 61% are female who were administered the questionnaire.

1.2 Age Composition

Table 1.2: Age of Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
18-24	22	17.6%
25-34	96	76.8%
35-44	5	4%
45-54	2	1.6%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 1.2: Age of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The above chart shows that out of 125 respondents, 17.6% belong to the 18-24 age group, 76.8% belong to the 25-34 age group, 4% belong to the 35-44 age group, and 1.6% belong to the 45-54 age group, respectively. Hence, the majority (80%) of the respondents hail from 25-34 age groups.

1.3 Nationality Composition

Table 1.3: Nationality of Respondents

Nationality	No. of Respondents	Percentage
India	125	100%
Other	0	0%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary Data

Chart 1.3: Nationality of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The above chart shows that out of 125 respondents, 100% are Indian and 0% is other. Hence, 100% of respondents are Indian.

1.4 Occupation Composition

Table 1.4: Occupation of Respondents

Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Student	72	57.6%
Housewife	2	1.6%
Employed	34	27.2%
Self-employed (Professional & Business)	17	13.6%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary Data

Chart 1.4: Occupation if Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart shows that out of 125 respondents, 57.6% are students, 1.6% are housewife, 27.2% are employed, and 13.6% are self-employed, respectively. Hence, the majority (57.6%) of the respondents are students.

1.5 Income Composition

Table 1.5: Income of Respondents

Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	85	68%
No	40	32%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 1.5: Income of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart shows that out of 125 respondents, only 68% have income.

1.6 Monthly Income Composition

Table 1.6: Monthly Income of Respondents

Monthly Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
0-20000	53	42.4%
20000-40000	31	24.8%
40000-60000	24	19.2%
More than 60000	17	13.6%
Total	125	100%

Chart 1.6: Monthly Income of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart shows that out of 125 respondents, 42% belong to the 0-20000, 25% belong to the 20000-40000, 19% belong to the 40000-60000, and 14% belong to the more than 60000 income group category, respectively. Hence, the majority (42%) of respondents belong to the 0-20000 income group category.

2 Lifestyle Measures of the Respondents

2.1 Purchase Composition in last three months

Table 2.1: Purchase Composition of Respondents

Often Purchase	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Once a week or more often	22	17.6%
At least once a month	58	46.4%
Less than once a month	45	36%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 2.1: Purchase Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart shows that out of 125 respondents, 18% purchase once a week or more often, 46% purchase at least once a month, and 36% purchase less than once a month. Hence, the majority (46%) of the respondents purchase green products at least once a month.

2.2 Type of Green Products Purchase composition in last three months

Table 2.2: Type of Purchase Composition of Respondents

Types of Green Products Purchased	No. of Respondents					Total
	The least purchased 1	Less purchased 2	Average purchased 3	More purchased 4	The most purchased 5	
Food	23	18	25	39	20	125
Health care/ cosmetic products	19	16	35	29	26	125
Cleaning products	24	27	37	24	13	125
Other household	31	22	30	25	17	125

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: In the above table, green products have been divided into four categories i.e. food, health care/ cosmetic products, cleaning products and other household products. It can be seen from the above table, firstly, out of 125 respondents in **food category** of green products, 23 have least purchased, 18 have less purchased, 25 are average purchased, 39 have more purchased, and 20 respondents have most purchased. Hence, the majority (39) of respondents have more purchased.

Secondly, out of 125 respondents in **health care/ cosmetic products** category of green products, 19 have least purchased, 16 have less purchased, 35 are average purchased, 29 have more purchased, and 26 respondents have most purchased. Hence, the majority (35) of respondents have average purchased.

Thirdly, out of 125 respondents in **cleaning products** category of green products, 24 have least purchased, 27 have less purchased, 37 are average purchased, 24 have more purchased, and 13 respondents have most purchased. Hence, the majority (37) of respondents have average purchased.

And, lastly, out of 125 respondents in **other household products** category of green products, 31 have least purchased, 22 have less purchased, 30 are average purchased, 25 have more purchased, and 17 respondents have most purchased. Hence, the majority (39) of respondents have more purchased.

Likert Scale Technique

3 Perception Measures of the Respondents

Agree or disagree perception levels of the respondents have been measured about green products in the following tables and charts.

3.1 Green products are good for the environment

Table 3.1:Green products are good for the environment

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	80	64%
Agree	33	26.4%
Neutral	1	0.8%
Disagree	3	2.4%
Strongly Disagree	8	6.4%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.1: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 64% strongly agree, 26% agree, 1% are neutral, 2% disagree, and 7% strongly disagree. Hence, the majority (64%) of the respondents strongly agree that green products are good for the environment.

3.2 Green products are healthy

Table 3.2: Green products are healthy

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	45	36%
Agree	64	51.2%
Neutral	11	8.8%
Disagree	2	1.6%
Strongly Disagree	3	2.4%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.2: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: the above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 36% strongly agree, 51% agree, 9% are neutral, 2% disagree, and 2% strongly disagree. Hence, the majority (51%) of the respondents agree that green products are healthy.

3.3 Green products have a good quality/ performance

Table 3.3: Green products have a good quality/ performance

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	21	16.8%
Agree	56	44.8%
Neutral	42	33.6%
Disagree	3	2.4%
Strongly Disagree	3	2.4%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.3: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: the above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 17% strongly agree, 45% agree, 34% are neutral, 2% disagree, and 2% strongly disagree. Hence, the majority (45%) of the respondents agree that green products have a good quality/ performance.

3.4 Green products have a better quality/ performance than conventional products

Table 3.4: Green products have a better quality/ performance than conventional products

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	19	15.2%
Agree	51	40.8%
Neutral	42	33.6%
Disagree	11	8.8%
Strongly Disagree	2	1.6%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.4: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: the above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 15% strongly agree, 41% agree, 34% are neutral, 9% disagree, and 1% strongly disagrees. Hence, the majority (41%) of the respondents agree that green products have a better quality/performance than conventional products.

3.5 Green products have a good taste and/ or good smell

Table 3.5: Green products have a good taste and/ or good smell

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	12	9.6%
Agree	52	41.6%
Neutral	51	40.8%
Disagree	8	6.4%
Strongly Disagree	2	1.6%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.5: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: the above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 9% strongly agree, 42% agree, 41% are neutral, 6% disagree, and 2% strongly disagree. Hence, the majority (42%) of the respondents agree that green products have a good taste and/ or smell.

3.6 Green products have a reasonable price

Table 3.6: Green products have a reasonable price

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	6	4.8%
Agree	21	16.8%
Neutral	35	28%
Disagree	52	41.6%
Strongly Disagree	11	8.8%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.6: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 5% strongly agree, 17% agree, 28% are neutral, 41% disagree, and 9% strongly disagree. Hence, the majority (41%) of the respondents disagree that green products have a reasonable price.

3.7 Green products are well promoted

Table 3.7: Green products are well promoted

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	13	10.4%
Agree	46	36.8%
Neutral	35	28%
Disagree	27	21.6%
Strongly Disagree	4	3.2%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.7: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 10% strongly agree, 37% agree, 28% are neutral, 22% disagree, and 3% strongly disagree. Hence, the majority (37%) of the respondents agree that green products are well promoted.

3.8 Green products are accessible/ available in the supermarket

Table 3.8: Green products are accessible/ available in the supermarket

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	7	5.6%
Agree	59	47.2%
Neutral	35	28%
Disagree	23	18.4%
Strongly Disagree	1	0.8%
Total	125	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3.8: Perception Composition of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: the above chart demonstrates that out of 125 respondents, 6% strongly agree, 47% agree, 28% are neutral, 18% disagree, and 1% strongly disagrees. Hence, the majority (47%) of the respondents agree that green products are accessible/ available in the supermarket.

Conclusion

It has been concluded that major of respondents are aware of green products and its benefits but they are not inclined towards purchase of green products over conventional products due to the fact that green products are highly priced and are not well promoted. Consumers face problems to differentiate between green products and conventional products. Demand of green products can only increase in market when price of green products are reasonable.

Suggestions for the future Study

Government and companies should work together to increase awareness among consumers, especially among male category of consumers and make them to shift their demand towards green products. Various campaigns and promotional activities can be conducted to motivate consumers to demand more of green products over conventional ones. Companies should focus towards advertisement to make aware consumers for availability, benefits of green products.

Limitation of the Study

This study has certain limitations. It includes only 125samples. Future study can focus on factors affecting ecological literacy of consumer purchase behaviour.

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